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V0.9	02/12/2025	First comprehensive draft after major review and update of original M6 plan. For Consortium feedback.
V1.0	16/12/2025	Final Draft further to Consortium Feedback - submission candidate

¹ **Type:** Use one of the following codes (in consistence with the Description of the Action):

R: Document, report (excluding the periodic and final reports)
DEM: Demonstrator, pilot, prototype, plan designs
DEC: Websites, patents filing, press & media actions, videos, etc.

² **Dissemination level:** Use one of the following codes (in consistence with the Description of the Action)

PU: Public, fully open, e.g. web
SEN: Sensitive, limited under conditions of the Grant Agreement

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List of Abbreviations and definitions

The abbreviations and definitions used in the deliverable are based on the AIDAVA Glossary [\[ref\]](#).

Executive Summary

This Deliverable provides an update to the Data Management Plan (DMP) for AIDAVA first published in M6 of the project under Deliverable 4.2[1]. As with the first version, the updated DMP is based on the European Commission Template for Horizon 2020 projects, though with additional features: in anticipation of the AI Act and European Health Data Space regulation enactments, partner i~HD has updated the DMP template to include a deeper consideration of the sustainability requirements for tooling that may be classed as a Medical Device and therefore High Risk AI System.

As Outlined in Deliverable 4.8[2] as the Regulatory Blueprint for the project, AIDAVA may be classed as a Medical Device and High Risk AI System. AIDAVA has therefore populated this Data Management Plan in line with recommended EC guidelines and the additional analysis run in D4.8 as well as learnings achieved throughout the last two years through the completion of the G1 evaluations and commencement of the G2 assessments.

A DMP is an important component of any data intensive programme because it imposes a need for balance between protection of data, success of the programme and the potential for reuse of data. AIDAVA is unique as a project because the primary data handling is focused on data ingestion and curation as a tool to assist citizens in managing their own health data. This clearly remains the case as the project commences its final year, where additional emphasis must be placed on the management of results data in particular to support the regulatory requirements for the Medical Device Regulation and AI Act. Both acts place an emphasis on record keeping for development and AI algorithm training data, its use and impact on the running of an AI system. A Data Management Plan keyed to sustainability is paramount.

The approach to developing the data management plan originally included workshop discussions with partners at the October 2022 Kick Off Meeting in Maastricht and a dedicated data flow workshop held in Tallinn in December 2023. Relevant activity has further included several iterations of development and dry run events both in person and online, including the May 2024 G1 prototype test run with patient participants and ongoing development of the software specifications throughout consortium meetings and working groups, including the AI Requirements Assessment working group described in D4.8.

The details gathered were compared with the proposal and obligations on the partners as described in the consortium agreement. They were also compared with the developing Research Protocols for both the Breast Cancer and Cardiovascular Disease (CVD) use cases developed in Task 1.4 and enhanced throughout the project lifetime and development of the G1 and G2 evaluations.

The results of the detail gathering are presented as the Data Management Plan in Section 3 of this Deliverable. It concludes with next steps and specification for future sustainability of AIDAVA post project.

1 Introduction

This Deliverable provides an updated Data Management Plan (DMP) for AIDAVA developing the first DMP published in M6 of the project under Deliverable 4.2[1]. This latest DMP is based on the European Commission Template for Horizon 2020 projects³ with additional features based on the recently enacted AI Act and European Health Data Space regulation. These updates have been implemented by partner i~HD to include a deeper consideration of the sustainability requirements for tooling that may be classed as a Medical Device and therefore High Risk AI System.

The purpose of the Data Management Plan remains to provide a basis upon which data will be handled and used to achieve the purposes of AIDAVA as well as ensure that maximum benefit can be derived from the project, including the adherence to the Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable (FAIR) Principles, Open Science agenda and informational self-determination for the individual citizen. This naturally has not changed as the project commences its final year, though AIDAVA and the wider innovation community must recognise that additional emphasis must be placed on the management of results and training data most notably to support the regulatory requirements for the Medical Device Regulation and AI Act. Both acts place an emphasis on record keeping for development and AI algorithm training data, its use and impact on the running of an AI system. A Data Management Plan keyed to sustainability is therefore paramount and must align traditional data management plan components with the evolving requirements for future regulatory compliance and a realistically sustainable solution post project.

This must still be balanced with the need to ensure that data relating to citizens, especially their health records, is protected in line with regulatory requirements, professional duties of confidence and the reasonable expectations of the citizens to have their personal data protected whilst also receiving the highest possible standards of care.

The DMP therefore has been completed in line with European Commission guidelines and with the future sustainability in mind. It provides a basis of how AIDAVA is achieving this balance and prepares for a future beyond the AIDAVA project. This latest DMP of course still contains details around AIDAVA's purposes, the data that is required, how it is and will be used potentially post-project, how it remains will be protected and how it might be used more widely where permissible. The DMP remains an integral part of the overall governance and risk assessment framework aligned with approaches defined in the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) and wider research governance processes, including development of research protocols and having received appropriate Research Ethics Committee (REC) approvals.

³ https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/h2020/gm/reporting/h2020-tpl-oa-data-mgt-plan_en.docx

2 Description of Activities

2.1 Reasons for a DMP

As outlined in the original DMP, a DMP is an important component of any data intensive programme because it imposes a need for balance between protection of data, success of the programme and the potential for reuse of data. AIDAVA is unique as a project because the primary data handling is focused on data ingestion and curation as a tool to assist citizens in managing their own health data. Their data are being transformed into an interoperable and reusable Personal Health Knowledge Graphs (PHKG). The data handling is for the benefit of the patient and treating physicians in clinical care, as well as for researchers, innovators and decision-makers in secondary data use. While the end goal is reusability, the scope of AIDAVA is first and foremost on data quality (there is limited value in sharing low quality data) to support the "curate once, use many times principle". To demonstrate this principle the project has been evaluating 3 cases of reuse: 1) delivery to a clinical registry in support of clinical research in BC, 2) computing a CVD risk score for treating physicians in clinical care, 3) displaying elements of the International Patient Summary (IPS) to the patient.

The latest DMP continues to address adherence to data protection and security regulations as well as addressing the concerns around security for the project duration and sustainability post project. These in turn relate to the need to ensure that data reuse is part of the respect for individual autonomy and privacy for participants. Whilst the DMP alone could not at the outset and still cannot provide assurance that these are addressed, it has and still does provide a basis to inform the activities that do, including the Data Protection by Design and Default and Data Protection Impact Assessment approaches documented under the Regulatory Framework Deliverable 4.4[3]

2.2 Approach

The approach to developing the DMP initially included workshop discussions with partners at the October 2022 Kick Off Meeting in Maastricht and a dedicated data flow workshop held in Tallinn in December 2023. In 2024, a test run of the G1 Prototype evaluation in Maastricht which also involved Patient Consultants allowed for a direct view of where the developments had reached and how data use and ongoing management requirements would need to be adapted from the original specifications in M6. These workshops allowed AIDAVA to gather plans and intentions around data handling and start to explore some of the particulars around how this would be achieved and thereafter how the plans were put into practice with the prototype test run.

In addition to these earlier workshops, the results of the G1 evaluation and lessons learned, and further development for the G2 evaluations provided a basis to reflect on data management considerations. The working group on AI Act compliance as outlined in D4.8 has also offered a basis on how to potentially evolve DMP templates to account for AI system data management along with ongoing data protection and technical review oversight, both from research ethics committees at the recruitment sites and the Ethical Advisory Board established by AIDAVA.

The details gathered were compared with the proposal and obligations on the partners as described in the consortium agreement. They were also compared with the developing Research Protocols for both the Breast Cancer and Cardiovascular Disease (CVD) use cases developed in Task 1.4 as they developed and were implemented across the G1 and G2 evaluations. The findings and conclusions are presented in Section 3.

3. Results & Discussion

3.1 Data summary

Integrated, high-quality personal health data (PHD) represents a potential wealth of knowledge for health care systems, but there is no reliable conduit for this data to become interoperable, AI-ready and reuse-ready at scale across institutions, at national and EU level.

AIDAVA has been filling this gap by prototyping and testing an AI powered, virtual assistant maximising automation of data curation & publishing of computable knowledge derived from unstructured and structured, heterogeneous data. The assistant includes a backend with a library of AI-based data curation tools and a frontend based on human-AI interaction modules that will help users when automation is not possible, while adapting to users' preferences. Two versions of this virtual assistant will be tested with hospitals and emerging health data intermediaries (HDIs), around breast cancer patient registries and longitudinal health records for cardio-vascular patients, in three languages.

The data in scope are described in detail in Deliverable D1.1[4] under Section 4.1 and 4.2 (subsection data source) for each of the use cases. This includes

- Medical Records from GP and mainly from hospitals, including structured and unstructured / narratives and diagnostic images, but excluding omics data;
- Patient held data from personal apps and/or medical devices

The data has been collated and curated into a Personal Health Knowledge Graph (PHKG), containing an interoperable patient longitudinal health record. The data curation process has been automated as much as possible through the orchestration of multiple tools, AI based tools and others; whenever automation is not possible - by lack of semantic - an "human in the loop" module has been used to assess if additional information should be requested to the patient or to an expert curator.

The curated PHKG can be reused for many different purposes. In the project, ADAIVA has focussed on

- extracts contributing to a "EU" federated breast cancer registry that support analytics across different sites - without transferring the data (use case 1) ,
- extracts to compute a cardiovascular risk score supporting monitoring of CVD patient (use case 2)
- Extracts - composed by the international patient summary (IPS) with visualisation of the data (both use cases).

AIDAVA has developed 2 generations of the virtual assistants as a prototype and has performed a formal assessment study as described in D1.4 to evaluate whether the prototype behaves as expected based on clear criteria and assess whether data are reusable. It has also provided a foundation for eventual Medical Device Regulation and High Risk AI System certification. During the assessment study, the recruitment has been limited to a small cohort of participants who were also offered the opportunity to enrol in the study if they wished to consent to participation. The assessment of the virtual assistant has occurred in parallel with usual care and has not been used to impact care (where in the event that participation revealed any findings of clinical significance, the treating physicians could be directly informed to take actions independently of the tool).

For these reasons AIDAVA did not at the outset anticipate that the data gathered would be of utility outside of the assessment study beyond any utility that participants may find for data that will be held by the HDI's. On completion of the G1 prototype evaluations and commencement of G2 evaluations, this remains the case, though data gathered is of importance to any sustainability efforts and pre-market authorisations that may be attempted after the project concludes.

These points are addressed in this updated DMP, with additional focus on sustainability and AI conformance aspects as outlined.

Aspect	Response/explanation
Purpose of the data collection/ generation and its relation to the objectives of the project	<p>Most of the data has been retrospective; only personal app and medical device app has been collected prospectively</p> <p>All data - retrospective and prospective - has been used to test the performance and acceptability of the prototype Virtual Assistant to transform dispersed and heterogeneous data source into an interoperable and reusable, Personal Health Knowledge Graph that can be reused for multiple purposes in clinical care (building a breast cancer registry) and clinical research (monitoring risk in CVD patients).</p> <p>AIDAVA considered at some of the sites the use of Synthetic data to assist in testing of the system operation, but this was ultimately abandoned in favour of using consented data as per the protocols.</p>
Types and formats of data generated or collected by the project	<p>Prospective: patient fitness and activity apps, and those supporting smart devices.</p> <p>These data have been managed by Health Data Intermediaries and ingested in the AIDAVA virtual assistant following a Data Transfer Agreement with the relevant HDI and a formal onboarding of the data sources, documented with metadata in a Data Source Catalogue.</p>
Any re-use of existing data and how this will be done	<p>Retrospective data: Medical records from primary and secondary care, all formats, including imaging but excluding omics items.</p> <p>These data are being managed by ingesting in the AIDAVA virtual assistant following a Data Transfer Agreement with the hospital and GP Practices, and a formal onboarding of the data sources, documented with metadata in a Data Source Catalogue.</p>
The origin of such data	Care provision, registry participation and personally collected data by the participants
Expected size of the data	<p>The "data" in scope of AIDAVA included potentially the whole electronic medical record - without images themselves (just the DICOM metadata) and without omics information - for breast cancer and CVD patients; there will be an expected 90 patients (45 breast cancer, 45 CVD).</p> <p>The size of this record (including hospital stays, hospital visits, GP follow-up, device and app data...) remains dependent upon the age of the patient, the length of time of their medical conditions and the seriousness of their condition.</p>
Likely users of the data	<p>Users of the systems</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Patient themselves (undertaking and validating the curation), recruited for assessing the prototype; they have been trained ● Community Curators - i.e. Patient Deputies ● Data Curators within the hospital sites who are responsible today for - often - manual curation

Aspect	Response/explanation
	Users of the curated data (Data users in the sense of DGA) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Breast cancer specialist ● CVD treating physician ● Patient themselves (visualisation),

Table 1: Data Summary

2.3 FAIR data

The main purpose of AIDAVA remains to build a medical device prototype that will take personal health data from heterogeneous data sources and make them Interoperable and Reusable.

When speaking about data in the context of AIDAVA, we speak about 2 types of data

1. The data sources (**DS**) - which include the raw data from the patient - coming from the hospital and - through the Health Data Intermediary - from GP, personal app and medical devices
2. The Personal Health Knowledge Graph (**PHKG**) which is generated from the data sources by the prototype medical device, into a curated, interoperable format. The PHKG can in turn be transformed into different target formats to support multiple different uses.

In the table below the difference between the 2 for each question is distinguished.

2.3.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

Aspect	Response/explanation
Are the data produced and/or used in the project discoverable, identifiable and locatable by means of a standard identification mechanism	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● DS: no, as the project is working with already collected data ● PHKG: not in scope but should be considered as the project proceeds
What standard identification mechanism used (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● DS: no, as the project is working with already collected data ● PHKG: not in scope
Is meta-data available through catalogue? Will it be offered in such a way that it can be harvested and indexed by other search engines and catalogues?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● DS: yes, the project has developed a catalogue for the data sources that will be curated into the PHKG ● PHKG: not in scope but should be considered as the project proceeds <p>Further searching and indexing outside of the consortium business and app use is not currently envisaged outside of the project due to the specific link to the project tool, but the reference to the approach for cataloguing may be shareable.</p>
Can meta-data be used for search?— i.e. Will search terms be provided in the metadata to optimize the possibility for	<p>Yes - the metadata we use within the PHKG includes provenance, workflow execution, and curation history. For DS, data description vocabulary and transformation configuration are used, which provide detailed information about the data sources. Suitable search terms include 'data</p>

Aspect	Response/explanation
discovery and then potential re-use?	description,' 'schema,' 'restrictions,' 'RDF mappings,' and 'transformation.
Naming conventions used	This will be agreed later in the project (where the internal Consortium processing may require a consistent naming convention as clinical variables are agreed)
Clear versioning supported?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● DS: no, as the project is working with already collected data ● PHKG: not in scope but should be considered as the project proceeds
Additional keyword search supported?	No, data will be accessed through the output specified in each use case (TBC)
What metadata will be created using which standards?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● DS metadata: DCAT-AP has been considered as an initial standard for metadata description; it has been widely enriched with more details on the content of each data source to support automation of the curation process. For DS, data description vocabulary and transformation configuration are used, which provide detailed information about the data sources. ● PHKG: the metadata we use within the PHKG includes provenance, workflow execution, and curation history

Table 2: Making Data FAIR

2.3.2 Making data openly accessible

Aspect	Response/explanation
Will data be made openly available as the default?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● DS: No (out of scope) ● PHKG: The data is only useful for AIDAVA purposes. Before considering using outside of AIDAVA for clinical care and/ or clinical research AIDAVA must assess the final data quality and validate the device following MDR and AI Act certification procedures. This point will be considered for eventual certification post project. Note that the entire premise of AIDAVA is to apply the FAIR principles so that individual citizens can ensure their data is Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable for them but can also join in making it FAIR for others, and always within their control.
Which datasets will NOT be openly available and why?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● DS: No (out of scope). ● PHKG: will not be made openly accessible as mentioned above
How will the data & meta-data be made accessible (e.g. by	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● DS: The cataloguing has followed standards for internal use. However, use of these data will be strictly limited by the Data Sharing Agreement

Aspect	Response/explanation
deposition in a stated repository)?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● PHKG: not considered (see above)
If a known repository, what arrangements are explored?	Not applicable
If project-specific access, then:	In line with the particulars of the Consortium wide Data Protection Impact Assessment and where appropriate, its Data Sharing Transfer and Data Licensing Agreements.
Data Access Committee	None planned, but an Ethical Advisory Board has been appointed and the project has always had Patient Association Organisations and Patient Consultants as equal partners.
Any conditions for access (i.e. a machine-readable license)	Likely N/A
What methods or software tools will be needed to access the data?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● DS: extract from data source and transfer to secure server (as specified in Data Sharing Agreements). ● PHKG: extract published in specific format/standard through the AIDAVA publishing module
Documentation for software	This has been developed with requirements for MDR and AI Act certification in focus (established requirements established in D4.8[2]).
Availability of software	Accessible by GitLab or GitHub internally to the project
Institution and researcher vetting process/procedures - describe	In line with the particulars of the Data Protection Impact Assessment where in the first instance data sharing was assessed by the Data Sources in line with their existing requirements and thereafter once the data is assembled centrally a decision have been made regarding which group can vet through the curation processes.

Table 3: Making Data Openly Accessible

2.3.3 Making data interoperable

Aspect	Response/explanation
Are the data produced in the project interoperable	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● DS: NO, used as such (heterogenous, not standardised) and transformed into the PHKG ● PHKG: yes, all PHKGs are an instance of a reference KG which will be based on SPHN RDF Schema (see https://www.biomedit.ch/rdf/sphn-schema/sphn), SNOMED, LOINC, ATC.
If not, explain why not	N/A

Aspect	Response/explanation
Data and metadata vocabularies, standards or methodologies used	HL7 FHIR profiles from IPS, SNOMED CT, LOINC (see as well description Deliverable 4.3 [5])
Standard vocabularies used	See above
Mappings from uncommon or project-specific ontologies or vocabularies to more commonly used ontologies	Initially AIDAVA did not anticipate the need to adopt uncommon ontologies or vocabularies; these would need to complement SNOMED where we considered to add some therapeutic areas specific terminologies. There have in fact been some local vocabularies used in the project, but AIDAVA has defined mappings from these to standard vocabularies. When a mapping is not available, AI-based entity-linking tools to identify potential mapping candidates during the curation process have been used.

Table 4: Making Data Interoperable

2.3.4 Increase data reuse (through clarifying licensing)

Aspect	Response/explanation
Will data be available for onward data-sharing/re-use?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● DS: no ● PHKG: yes - the end purpose of AIDAVA is to <u>curate data, reuse many times</u>. In the context of the prototype there are 3 types of extract <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Mimicking a EU breast cancer registry ○ Input for assessment CVD risk score ○ Support the International Patient Summary (IPS) for patient visualisation
Approach to data licensing for onward use	N/A as the PHKG from the patient are resulting from an invalidated/ uncertified prototype. The Project will explore the possibility of keeping the data in the control of the participant at its completion as well and allow them to decide with whom this can be shared.
Likely date for data availability for onward use	N/A as the PHKG from the patient are resulting from an invalidated/ uncertified prototype but this will be explored as part of a market authorised tool.
Explain any restriction on date of availability	N/A
Possible restrictions on onward data-sharing	Data is unlikely to be shared onward, as the PHKG from the patient is resulting from an invalidated/ uncertified prototype. The end objective however of AIDAVA is to ensure high quality data so that the patient can share high quality data and this may be implemented as functionality of a market authorised tool.

Aspect	Response/explanation
Data retention policy (including availability for data-sharing)	<p>Will follow data retention policies as determined at sites. Evaluation/open access data will be retained according to Consortium feasibility checks and wider EC guidance.</p> <p>NB: as the PHKG data are not for further used after then end of the project; AIDAVA will need to agree whether they should be kept or deleted after the end of the project depending on regulatory requirements or any Medical Device Certification, or where the participants may be able to retain the data at the end of the study.</p> <p>This remains the case and part of the assessments for retention and sustainability activities. This may require reverting back to ethics committees to confirm retention is possible.</p>
Description of data quality assurance processes	<p><i>Task 4.2 has developed statistical assessment methodologies and tools to define metrics, to help flag up issues of bias in the data quality enhancement and FAIRification process. This will assure that the PHKG will be based on high-quality data.</i></p> <p>For the PHKG: A dedicated task within T4.2 was assigned to assure data quality using specific methods developed by partner i~HD to assess and label the data from a quality perspective. The results are available under Deliverable 4.3 [5]</p>

Table 5: Increase Data Re-use (through clarifying licences)

2.3.5 Allocation of resources

Aspect	Response/explanation
Estimated project costs for making data FAIR	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● DS: N/A ● PHKG: to be estimated in terms of workload as part of the assessment
Data management responsibility across the project	<p>Each clinical site/ hospital has taken lead responsibility for the data managed within their hospital - including the resulting PHKG managed within their site. They have liaised closely with participants and HDIs in discharging this responsibility, where the responsibilities of participants and HDIs have been established in the sharing agreements. The developer of the curation tool has supported deployment and use of the prototype; they have been responsible for ensuring secure processing not for the content of the data.</p>
Resources required for long term preservation (costs and potential value, who decides and how what data will be kept and for how long)	<p>This needs to be scoped out as the sustainability plans develop around looking to develop the tool as a certified High Risk AI System Medical Device. This will determine the specific costs around any retention of data and resources for further developing the tool as a market authorised product.</p>

Aspect	Response/explanation

Table 6: Allocation of Resources

2.3.6 Data security

Aspect	Response/explanation
Data security measures used (including data recovery as well as secure storage and transfer of sensitive data)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● DS: data transferred by DTA continues to be managed within a Docker instance deployed in each clinical site and under their local responsibility ● PHKG: as above. <p>A number of information governance and data protection and information security instruments have been used in and are specified throughout Deliverables D4.4[3], D4.8[2] and other development deliverables.</p>
Where data will safely be stored (in certified repositories for long-term preservation and curation). Provide detail	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● DS: data transferred by DTA will be managed within a Docker instance deployed in each clinical site ● PHKG: dito <p>For the existing modelling and risk stratification work within the Consortium, the security and certification requirements are being assessed as part of the processes described in the DPIA</p>

Table 7: Data Security

2.3.7 Ethical aspects

Aspect	Response/explanation
Any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing	<p>Independent ethical oversight has been achieved via Independent Review Boards for each of the Clinical Partner sites where participants will be recruited.</p> <p>AIDAVA has also appointed an independent Ethical Advisory Board of Experts who have been operating for over two years. Their annual reports are available under deliverables D4.5[6] and D4.9[7].</p> <p>Data use and sharing have been considered at both levels where the EAB provides pan-project oversight and recommendations and the IRBs provide local, partner specific advisory and oversight as part of research governance regulations.</p>

Aspect	Response/explanation
References to ethics deliverables and ethics chapter in the Description of the Action (DoA) – if relevant	WP4 - D4.5[6] and D4.9[7]
Questionnaires dealing with personal data	Participants have been given user feedback questionnaires as part of the Assessment studies in G1 and will be provided this in G2 evaluations
How is informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation sought in such questionnaires?	This has been handled pursuant to Research Ethics Approval and sought at clinical sites according to an ethically approved standard operating procedure as specified in the Study Assessment Protocol, approved by each local IRB.

Table 8: Ethical Aspects

2.3.8 Sustainability and Future Compliance Risk Management

Aspect	Response/explanation
What elements are planned for sustainability activities moving forward?	<p>Plans for developing AIDAVA as an interventional tool are underway. This will include all components including AI driven components as part of a fully integrated chatbot tool.</p> <p>Of specific relevance will be validation on the potential of AIDAVA to decrease the overall cost of EHDS implementation (generation of critical data categories in EEHRxF, and answer to HDAB queries)</p>
What certifications would be required for a sustainability plan to go to market? (e.g. MDR, AI Certifications)	<p>The following regulations would likely require certifications</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● MDR 2023 (Medical Device Regulation) as a Class IIa Medical Device on the basis that information provided will inform clinical practice and decision making; ● HTA (Health Technology Assessments) are likely expected for state-funded interventions ● AI Act 2024 would likely define this as a high-risk AI System given the Medical Device Classification

Aspect	Response/explanation
<p>What data retention and best practice documentation is required to achieve this? Specifically how can we ensure the quality, assessment of bias, traceability of results and recommendations, transparency, repeatability etc.</p>	<p>Results from the data processing and algorithm training for the AI Components will need to be retained for record keeping and documentary evidence around the algorithm development.</p> <p>Copies of the training data will also need to be retained.</p> <p>Data Quality and Bias assessments will likely need to be executed during the post project product development phase.</p> <p>Requirements are fully outlined under Deliverable D4.8[2].</p> <p>The instructions manuals and videos describing AIDAVA use will need to be enhanced for product development.</p>
<p>What risk management is envisaged to support sustainability? E.g. DPIA Updates, Ethical Review, Tool management, Legacy System reliance etc.</p>	<p>An update (or potentially redrafting) of the Project DPIA will be needed and partners in the ongoing sustainability phase will likely need to (re)run their DPIAs.</p> <p>It is likely that the IRBs will need to reassess the ongoing use of data and tooling for the product development phase post project; this is either via an amendment to the existing ethics approvals or a brand new application may need to be sought depending on the requirements of each participating site and their local legislature.</p>
<p>Is there a data flow diagram available?</p>	<p>Please refer to the DPIA and technical development deliverables.</p>

Table 9: Sustainability and Future Compliance Risk Management

2.4 Information Asset Register

AIDAVA has kept an Information Asset Register in the form of a metadata catalogue as part of the curation process. This accounts for each of the data holder partners' contributions, data flows and sample transfers across the two use cases. The Register has been achieved through the Data Source Catalogue in Task 3.4 (outlined Deliverable 3.3, designated SENSITIVE) and the requirements established in Task 1.3.

The importance of the Information Assets Register has been to be able to establish the types of data being used for the project and what each of the parties within the project are doing with those data. This being a data source providing data, a recipient processing data or indeed both. Further registration within the IAO for future plans including the sustainability and product development phase must be documented.

This register helps to link data items, activities and responsibilities to the agreements, approvals and oversight requirements (including entry into the DPIA). This way AIDAVA has been able to account for not only the continued update of proposed data flows, but also isolate where there may have been

delays or uncertainties around data transfers. This is also important for the Machine Learning and VA validation, including the requisite Data Quality checks.

The IAO is foundational for any ongoing activities around further product development and market authorisation, especially given the likelihood of Medical Device and High Risk AI System Classification. As product development plans start to develop, the IAO should also build upon the specifications outlined in D4.8 and include a record of the algorithm training heuristics and training data sets along with results of data quality and bias assessments to date.

3 Conclusion

AIDAVA remains a unique project whose primary goal is to empower citizens to be able to access and manage - and increase the quality of - their own health records and support their care teams in managing their conditions. It continues to endeavour to give citizens unprecedented control over their health information and use it as they see fit and offer valuable insights to their care teams.

In evaluating the approach AIDAVA has taken over the last three years this updated DMP is trying to balance the unique nature of the data processing with adherence to high standards of data protection whilst honouring the FAIR Principles, supporting Open Science where possible as well as data utility for citizens within the Health Data Intermediary model. During the course of the project and since the first DMP was published back in M6, additional requirements for future proofing this unique tool have started to crystallise, as outlined in the Regulatory Conformance Analysis Deliverable D4.8[2]. This has meant that an update to Data Management Planning as outlined in this deliverable has been required.

In order to achieve the latest goals for the project and its future after its completion in nearly a year's time, the approach that AIDAVA has taken to governance has continued to reflect the need to support the data use within the scope of the assessment studies and the extent to which it empowers citizens and their care teams. This DMP outlines how AIDAVA has and will continue to :

- Ensure that the assessment of the prototypes has been appropriately risk assessed and governed according to contract between the data handling parties and service providers;
- Enabling the participants in the assessment of the prototypes to control the curation of their health data and its reuse where this has been assured via review of the assessment protocol established in D1.4 and its development for G2;
- Consider how data generated by the project, including the Personal Health Knowledge Graphs, might have been made available for further reuse at the behest of the participants and the Project with respect to the FAIR Principles and OpenData Principles where its utility for these is minimal outside of the project;
- Assess and prepare for post-project activity in enhancing the prototype and evaluated G2 version for full product development and planning for eventual market authorisation

This updated DMP reflects on the experience of AIDVAA and its G1 evaluation, its G2 evolution and considers the immediate and longer term goals and impacts of the project. Through the various activities and published deliverables the approaches AIDAVA has taken have been assessed in line with the protocols of the studies that are being defined under D1.2 and 1.4 and since updated.

Further development of approaches have been outlined to support post-project product development and certifications for market authorisation as a likely Class IIa Medical Device that is an AI System as outlined on the MDR and AI Act.

4 Next steps

This deliverable will support the ongoing G2 evaluations and project completion, as well as serve as a basis for developing a product development plan post project. The regulatory compliance measures as part of the rest of Task 4.1 will align with the design and development of the AIDAVA tooling as part of post-project activity. These include review of the DPIA and identification of specific retention and reporting requirements for concluding the evaluations and evolving the AIDAVA tool as a market authorised product.

As the tooling reaches maturity after the G2 evaluations, its potential as a full product can be more effectively realised. The regulatory compliance requirements will continue to be met as AIDAVA evolves where Task 4.1 has and will continue to oversee AIDAVA through to project completion and the process of product development which will enter a product authorisation process. The DMP and regulatory activities as well as the activities will continue to be provided for additional trialling as may be required as part of further product development and market authorisation, including any new assessment study protocols, study information packages/participant information leaflets and associated consent forms.

5 References

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6 Annexes (if applicable)

N/A